

1 **NKG7 inhibition for management of acute rejection in solid organs and hematopoietic stem cell**
2 **transplant.**

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7 The concept here outlines that NKG7 is both a marker of and transmitter of signals critical for pathways
8 relevant to rejection. Evidence suggesting NKG7 also coordinates immune-mediated clearance of
9 transformed cells therapeutic indicates risk of malignancy with transplant-associated NKG7 targeting.
10 Given redundancy in signaling pathways important for clearance of transformed or genomically unstable
11 cells through Tyd, NK and CD8+ and HLA-V/KIR2DL3, the benefits of managing an acute rejection
12 reaction may likely outweigh malignancy associated risks. Importantly, the basic, translational and clinical
13 concepts here serve as an introduction to development of advanced, targeted therapeutics used in
14 transplant medicine and in autoimmune disease, tools and concepts that might otherwise be considered
15 difficult or high-risk based on nature of content.

16 Citations

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1. Ng, S.S., De Labastida Rivera, F., Yan, J., Corvino, D., Das, I., Zhang, P., Kuns, R., Chauhan, S.B., Hou, J., Li, X.Y. and Frame, T.C., 2020. The NK cell granule protein NKG7 regulates cytotoxic granule exocytosis and inflammation. *Nature immunology*, 21(10), pp.1205-1218.
 2. Li, X.Y., Corvino, D., Nowlan, B., Aguilera, A.R., Ng, S.S., Braun, M., Cillo, A.R., Bald, T., Smyth, M.J. and Engwerda, C.R., 2022. NKG7 is required for optimal antitumor T-cell immunity. *Cancer immunology research*, 10(2), pp.154-161.